

Volumetric insights into urban growth analysis: Investigating vertical and horizontal patterns

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ABSTRACT

Urban expansion has traditionally been studied in terms of horizontal sprawl, overlooking the role of vertical densification. This paper adopts a volumetric approach to analyze the spatiotemporal dynamics of urban growth in the Tehran Metropolitan Region (TMR) from 1985 to 2024, addressing two key objectives: (a) to examine border patterns of volumetric growth, demographic shifts, and intra-urban variations, and (b) to identify the underlying drivers of volumetric expansion. Using Landsat imagery, Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) data, and population statistics from the Statistical Center of Iran, we apply spatial-statistical methods and the XGBoost-SHAP machine learning framework to assess urban expansion patterns and their driving forces. Our findings reveal a transition from vertical densification to horizontal sprawl, with urban expansion increasingly adopting an outward trajectory. Intra-urban analysis uncovers a diffusion-coalescence pattern, where vertical densification often follows horizontal expansion but can also occur concurrently. While older urban segments continue to densify vertically due to land scarcity, newly developed areas exhibit distinct volumetric characteristics, reflecting a cyclical interplay between centralization and decentralization. The XGBoost-SHAP analysis highlights a shift in driving forces from spatial inertia to population-driven growth and, more recently, to economic and geographic constraints. By integrating remote sensing, spatial analysis, and machine learning, this study provides a systematic and data-driven framework for understanding the spatiotemporal dynamics of urban expansion and its underlying drivers. The findings underscore the importance of integrated urban planning strategies that balance vertical and horizontal growth, optimize land use, and enhance sustainability. Incorporating volumetric analysis into planning frameworks can foster more adaptive, resource-efficient, and resilient urban development.

1. Introduction

Urbanization has intensified globally, with the global urban population rising from 30 % in 1950 to 55 % today and projected to reach 68 % by 2050 (United Nations, 2022). A critical challenge is metropolitan areas expanding spatially at a faster rate than their population growth, leading to inefficient, low-density urban forms (Behnisch et al., 2022; Denis, 2020; Xu et al., 2020). Empirical studies reveal distinct regional trajectories: while cities in the Global North favor compact, inward-oriented development driven by policies enhancing land-use efficiency, those in the Global South continue to experience rapid outward expansion due to high population growth, weak planning

regulations, and unregulated land markets (Chakraborty et al., 2022; Mahтта et al., 2022). As a result, understanding urban expansion dynamics is increasingly critical, as it shapes environmental sustainability, resource efficiency, and long-term urban resilience, particularly in the rapidly growing metropolises of the Global South.

An extensive body of literature has established that urban density and spatial configuration play a critical role in determining environmental performance, energy use, and livability (Ding et al., 2022). Compact urban form, when aligned with mixed land use and transit accessibility, has been shown to reduce per capita energy consumption and transportation-related carbon emissions (Ewing & Cervero, 2010; Rode et al., 2017). However, recent studies emphasize that density alone

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is not inherently sustainable; benefits depend on achieving optimal density thresholds that balance resource efficiency with infrastructure capacity and quality of life (Dehghani et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2018). From an urban ecology perspective, the spatial arrangement of green infrastructure, surface permeability, and ventilation corridors significantly influences microclimates, urban heat island intensity, and ecosystem services (Gill et al., 2007; Norton et al., 2015). In parallel, the resilience literature underscores the need to integrate spatial form with hazard mitigation—particularly in cities exposed to climate shocks or seismic risks. Research shows that urban configurations that decentralize risk, ensure redundancy in infrastructure, and preserve emergency access routes tend to be more adaptive under stress (Cutter et al., 2008; Azizi et al., 2022).

The trajectory of urban expansion form is influenced by local factors such as geography, policy, and economic conditions factors, affecting how cities evolve, densify, and transform over time (Güneralp et al., 2020; Soltani et al., 2025a). A common hypothesis is that urban growth follows wave-like trends, with two main phases: diffusion and coalescence. The diffusion phase involves outward low-density spread into undeveloped areas, while the coalescence phase merges these dispersed zones into continuous urban areas, increasing density. Though this pattern is widely observed (Dietzel et al., 2005; Charles Dietzel et al., 2005; Allan et al., 2022), exceptions suggest that urban growth does not always follow a predictable or linear path. Scholars have focused on identifying and explaining the patterns of urban growth, which typically emerge through three distinct modes: outlying growth (low-density, dispersed development into rural or undeveloped areas), edge expansion (urban peripheries forming suburban neighborhoods and commercial areas), and infill development (increased density within existing urban areas through underused land) (Liu et al., 2010). Studies often examine how these growth modes shift in dominance over time and space. Previous research indicates that the three growth modes often appear together, but their prominence waxes and wanes with the urbanization cycle, determining the dominant growth phase (Chakraborty et al., 2022). Li et al. (2013) describe this as a "spiraling process" of shifting dominance among the growth modes. Novotný et al. (2022) argue that urban expansion occurs through a sequential co-occurrence of these modes, rather than simultaneous. These growth patterns can be further subdivided into broader twofold process of urbanization: urban expansion, which refers to horizontal growth, and urban densification, also known as infill development.

However, Cities are three-dimensional, and urban growth occurs in one of three ways: (1) lateral spreading into peripheral non-urban lands, (2) increasing built density through the development of un- or underutilized land within existing urban areas, often called infilling, or (3) vertical growth of built-up structures (Chakraborty et al., 2022; Mahtta et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2020). despite the plethora of vertical urban typologies, the traditional analysis reflecting a horizontal mindset and overlook the vertical dimension of urbanization, which plays a crucial role in urban density. The evolution of urban growth from horizontal to vertical growth signifies a fundamental transformation in urban development, with the increasing trend in building heights in major cities underscoring upward growth as a global phenomenon (Domingo et al., 2023; He et al., 2023). For example, while the findings of horizontal mindset studies such as Novotný et al. (2022) indicated that China had the most outlying growth than North American, the global comparative analysis by Mahtta et al. (2019) found that Chinese cities show more upward growth than cities in the west (North and CS America). These examples highlight significant regional variations in urban expansion patterns and expose a major limitation in traditional 2D urban form analyses—the omission of vertical growth. Therefore, A key challenge remains: how can densification and compactness be accurately measured? Relying solely on two-dimensional (2D) data fails to capture actual building density and land use intensity. Instead, urban form studies must integrate three-dimensional (3D) metrics to provide a more comprehensive understanding true nature of urban growth, especially in

rapidly developing regions where urban growth is more upward than outward are concentrated in the East and Southeast Asia (E and SE Asia) and the Middle East (Mahtta et al., 2019).

With growing attention to the vertical dimension of urban development, several studies have attempted to explore vertical characteristics of urban built-up environments (Domingo et al., 2023; Hewitt & Graham, 2015; Munn & Dragičević, 2020). Height-based approaches have been widely applied to tracked changes in building heights in cities (He et al., 2019; Shi et al., 2009), such as of Floor Area Ratio (FAR), have been employed to measure the vertical-to-horizontal growth ratio and assess the impact of vertical development on urban density (Salvati et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2022; Zambon et al., 2019). Recent advancements in remote sensing and GIS technologies, particularly through LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) and SAR (Synthetic Aperture Radar) data, have significantly improved the availability and accuracy of height data for urban studies, facilitated the study of changes in 3D urban form over longer periods, including spatiotemporal change detection, densification analysis, and modeling of three-dimensional growth (Geiß et al., 2019; Huang & Stouffs, 2024; Lin et al., 2014; Manawadu & Wijeratne, 2022; Yu et al., 2010; Zhao et al., 2020). Several studies have examined both horizontal and vertical urban expansion to understand regional variations in urban growth patterns. Zhang et al. (2018) analyzed the horizontal and vertical expansion of three capital megacities—Beijing, Seoul, and Tokyo—between the late 1980s and mid-2010s. Zhou et al. (2021) investigated variations in urban built-up density shaped by vertical expansion across different cities and regions over time. More recently, researchers in urban planning have extended the concept of vertical urban development toward a "volumetric" understanding of urbanism, recognizing the need to integrate horizontal and vertical growth into a unified metric (Bruyns et al., 2021; Hsu & Han, 2024; McNeill, 2019, 2020). The "Urban Volume" metric has been introduced to bridge these dimensions of expansion (Estoque et al., 2015; Frokking et al., 2022; Ge et al., 2021; Koomen et al., 2009). Some scholars, such as Zhao et al. (2020) and Domingo et al. (2023), introduced 3D urban morphology frameworks, categorizing urban form dynamics into types such as "intensification," "sprawling expansion," and "efficient expansion." Ans has provided valuable insights into the spatial complexity of 3D urban form evolution.

While research on urban vertical growth and 3D morphology has expanded, these studies primarily focus on broad urban trends rather than examining how vertical densification varies across different intra-urban spatial structures. To address this limitation, our study uses a volumetric approach using the urban volume index, which captures both horizontal and vertical dimensions of urban growth. our approach attempts to provide a more comprehensive understanding of urban transformation by distinguishing between newly developed areas, where volume reflects both the footprint and height of new constructions, and older urban areas, where an increase in volume signifies vertical densification. Furthermore, instead of relying on static administrative boundaries, which may not accurately represent urban growth patterns, we apply temporal segmentation to analyze urban expansion across different time periods. By dividing urban development into distinct temporal phases, we can track the sequential co-occurrence of horizontal expansion and vertical densification, revealing how new urban areas emerge while older parts of the city become denser over time. Using the Tehran Metropolitan Region (TMR)—a rapidly expanding metropolitan area in the Global South—as a case study, we investigate two key research objectives:

- (1) border patterns of volumetric growth, demographic shifts, and intra-urban variations, and
- (2) the underlying drivers of volumetric expansion.

2. Methods and materials

2.1. Case study

TMR (Fig. 1) is situated in northern Iran on the slopes of the Alborz Mountain and encompasses Tehran and Karaj, the area's most populous and expansive cities. As the capital of Iran and one of the fastest-growing cities in Asia, TMR had a population exceeding 16.5 million in 2016 (Statistical Center of Iran, 2016). This region, spanning approximately 18,884 km², functions as Iran's cultural, commercial, financial, political, and social nucleus, accommodating roughly 20 % of the nation's population and representing its most industrialized area.

The TMR has emerged as a central hub for migration from other regions of the country, mostly due to the presence of job prospects, healthcare facilities, educational services, and social welfare amenities (Shahraki et al., 2012). In recent decades, the region has experienced tremendous urbanization, driven by substantial population growth, considerable migration from rural to urban areas, and a quick surge in the construction of new industries outside of TMR's central area. The urban growth is exacerbated by the concentrated centralization of government operations in the capital, leading to a hierarchical urban structure that is predominantly controlled by Tehran city (Rajaei & Mansourian, 2016).

The TMR has grown unchecked in Iranian cities due to a lack of spatial fairness, worsening the nation's population disparity. Nevertheless, the exorbitant cost of living, excessive traffic congestion, and air pollution in TMR have resulted in a significant influx of people toward the neighboring cities (Seifolddini & Mansourian, 2014). The phenomenon of urbanization and expansion in agricultural regions located south of TMR's (Shahraki et al., 2012), specifically along the Karaj River and the Varamin plain, has caused numerous villages to be transformed into cities of varying sizes, including small, intermediate, and major cities (Shoorcheh et al., 2016). Rural areas adjacent to the primary road networks around Tehran city, characterized by affordable land and lax regulation, possess a significant capacity for urbanization. Construction is currently taking place in flatlands, hills, mountains, and riversides (Alaei Moghadam et al., 2018). Furthermore, the issue of housing has emerged as a significant challenge across the majority of Iran's megacities, namely in Tehran City and Karaj (Dianati, 2021). The establishment of new urban centers has been prioritized to curb the unchecked expansion of current cities and to disperse the population (Dadashpoor & Alidadi, 2017). Over the past two decades, several new

cities have been established, such as Pardis, located 30 km east of TMR; Andisheh, situated 20 km west of TMR; and Hashtgerd, found northwest of Karaj.

2.2. Data and analytics

The research methodology, illustrated in Fig. 2, adopts a multi-faceted approach to analyzing urban growth and population distribution through satellite imagery and diverse data sources. The process begins with the acquisition of Landsat images from multiple years, which are processed using the Maximum Likelihood Classification (MLC) method and analyzed within Google Earth Engine (GEE) to delineate built-up areas. To enhance the spatial analysis, urban volume layers are extracted from the Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL), while population data is integrated from the Statistical Center of Iran. A combination of spatial and statistical techniques is employed to examine urban expansion patterns. Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) and global and local Moran's I are applied to assess spatial dependencies and variations in urban growth. Additionally, segmental analysis is conducted to capture intra-urban variations and structural changes over time. To identify key driving forces behind vertical urban growth, the study leverages the XGBoost-SHAP machine learning framework, which quantifies the relative impact of economic, geographic, and demographic factors. By integrating remote sensing, spatial analysis, and machine learning, this methodology provides a systematic and data-driven framework for understanding the spatiotemporal dynamics of urban expansion and its underlying drivers.

2.2.1. Built-up data

In this research, "built-up areas" refer to land transformed from its natural state to accommodate human settlements and infrastructure. To identify the urban footprint, built-up areas were calculated for 1985, 1995, 2005, 2015, and 2024 using Landsat satellite imagery. The sensors utilized included Landsat 5 TM (Thematic Mapper) for 1985 and 1995, Landsat 7 ETM+ (Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus) for 2005, and Landsat 8 OLI (Operational Land Imager) for 2015 and 2024. This process was facilitated using GEE and the Maximum Likelihood Classification (MLC) method. Initially, Landsat images for the specified years were imported into GEE, where cloud masking and atmospheric correction were applied. Training areas for different land cover classes were defined, and the MLC algorithm was employed. For the study, land uses were classified into built-up and non-built-up areas, focusing on

Fig. 1. Location of TMR.

Fig. 2. Research process and research questions addressing methods.

extracting regions representing the urban footprint. Additionally, the accuracy of the classifications was assessed using the Kappa coefficient, with values of 0.77, 0.81, 0.85, 0.90, and 0.93 for the years 1985, 1995, 2005, 2015, and 2024, respectively. Urban layers were resampled to a spatial resolution of 100 × 100 m to ensure consistency and ease of analysis. The final built-up maps are presented in Fig. 3.

2.2.2. Urban volume data

In this study, "urban volume" refers to the three-dimensional extent of built-up areas. This would encompass the total space occupied by buildings and structures within a city or urban area. It considers the ground area covered by buildings (like built-up areas) and their height. The Urban volume data (GHS-BUILT-V) was obtained from the Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) and spans several time periods with a precise 100-meter resolution, expressed in cubic meters. This comprehensive dataset is produced by meticulously assessing diverse satellite images, including those from Sentinel-2, Landsat, and global digital elevation model (DEM) data, as utilized in previous works such as Sarker et al. (2024) to determine the volume of built-up areas for the TMR, GHSL data were imported into GEE and carefully superimposed on built-up extent layers from 1985, 1995, 2005, 2015, and 2024. This phase was essential for precisely establishing the spatial extent of urbanized regions and ensuring spatial consistency. This procedure ensured that the volumetric calculations only considered structures constructed by humans, resulting in a more precise estimate of the volume of built-up areas. The 3D schematic of the urban volume is depicted in Fig. 2.

2.2.3. Population data

The population data for 1985, 1995, 2005, 2015, and projected estimates for 2024 were acquired from the Statistical Center of Iran (Statistical Center of Iran, 2020). Originally, population census data were presented in statistical blocks that exhibited variations in both size and shape. The blocks were converted into a standardized grid format to ensure a constant spatial resolution across all datasets. The population data was aggregated using zonal analysis methods in Geographic

Information Systems (GIS). The data was summarized into a grid of polygons with cell sizes of 100 × 100 m, which were retrieved from built-up layers. This procedure entailed superimposing the statistical blocks onto the grid and computing the population within each grid cell by considering the proportion of the block's area that intersected with each cell. The resultant population density layer offers a meticulous spatial depiction of the population dispersion at a superior resolution. The grid contains cells representing the number of residents per hectare, enabling accurate examination of population density in urban and suburban regions.

2.3. Analytical methods

2.3.1. Segmental analysis and metrics

The segmental analysis methodology provides a sophisticated framework for understanding incremental urban growth and densification trends. By dividing the study area into temporal segments aligned with key urban development milestones—1955, 1985, 2005, 2015, and 2024—this approach facilitates a detailed and multidimensional evaluation of urbanization dynamics. metrics such as the Volume-to-Area ratio (V/A) are integral to this methodology, offering insights into the transition from horizontal sprawl to a more compact and sustainable urban form by emphasizing vertical growth in response to population pressure and land constraints. Metrics of Population per Area (P/A) and Population per Volume (P/V) further enhance the analysis by focusing on the spatial and volumetric distribution of people, reflecting the level and nature of urban intensification. Segmental analysis provides two main advantages. First, it helps track how specific segments evolve over time, revealing patterns of change and development. Second, it enables comparisons between different areas, highlighting differences in growth and urban characteristics. This approach offers a clear understanding of both temporal and spatial dynamics, aiding effective urban planning.

2.3.2. Moran's I spatial auto-correlation analysis

Spatial autocorrelation analysis is essential in this study to understand how urban growth patterns in the TMR are spatially related and

Fig. 3. The presentation of urban volume (left) and built-up areas (right) of TMR.

whether similar growth trends cluster together or are dispersed across the region. This analysis provides insights into how neighboring areas influence each other, which is critical for revealing the underlying socio-economic and infrastructural drivers of urban expansion. To assess these spatial relationships, the study employed Global Moran's I, a statistical measure used to evaluate overall spatial autocorrelation (Chen et al., 2021). The initial step involves generating a contiguity structure that defines the spatial relationships between the geographic units under investigation. We selected a queen contiguity spatial weights matrix to model neighboring relationships, as it captures spatial interactions more inclusively by considering shared boundaries or vertices between geographic units (Peluso et al., 2024). This approach was preferred over rook contiguity, which only considers shared boundaries, and distance-based weights, which can obscure local spatial variation by averaging over distance thresholds. Our focus on local spatial

heterogeneity made contiguity-based methods more appropriate for the analysis. Moran's I statistic ranges from -1 to $+1$, where a positive Moran's I value indicates clustering (meaning similar values are clustered together), a negative value suggests dispersion (where neighboring units have dissimilar values), and a value near zero implies randomness. The mathematical formula of global Moran I is presented in Eq. (1): (Anselin, 1995).

$$I = \frac{N}{W} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij} (x_i - \bar{x})(x_j - \bar{x})}{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- I: Global Moran's I statistic
- N: Total number of spatial units (locations)

W : Sum of all spatial weights w_{ij}

w_{ij} : Spatial weight between units i and j (typically from a spatial weights matrix)

x_i : Value of the variable at location iii

\bar{x} : Mean of the variable across all spatial units

x_j : Value of the variable at location jjj

Moran's I Local spatial association significance — that is, a LISA cluster map. To visualize the results of the LISA, we mapped the spatial clustering of the five cluster categories for each variable:

High-High: Includes areas where the region and its neighboring regions have high values for the variable being analyzed.

Low-Low: Encompasses regions where the region and its neighbors exhibit low values.

High-Low: Identifies regions that have high values but are surrounded by neighboring areas that have low values.

Low-High: Includes areas with low values surrounded by neighboring regions with high values.

Non-Significant: Comprises regions that do not show any statistically significant spatial association with their neighbors.

(Anselin, 1995).

$$I_i = (y_i - \bar{y}) \sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij} (x_j - \bar{x}) \quad (2)$$

I_i is the local LISA statistic for location i .

y_i is the value of the dependent variable (e.g., urban volume) at location i .

\bar{y} is the mean of the dependent variable.

x_j is the value of the independent variable (e.g., population density) at location j .

\bar{x} is the mean of the independent variable.

w_{ij} is the spatial weight between location i and location j , representing the spatial influence or proximity.

2.3.3. GWR analysis

A GWR analysis was conducted to evaluate the spatial heterogeneity between the distribution of urban volume (dependent variable) and population density. This method allows for assessing how the relationship between urban volume and population density varies across different spatial locations. GWR (Eq. (3)) is particularly useful in spatial data analysis because it extends traditional regression models by allowing coefficients to vary geographically, capturing local variations in the relationship between variables.

(Fotheringham et al. 2009).

$$y_i = \beta_0(u_i, v_i) + \sum_{k=1}^p \beta_k(u_i, v_i) x_{ik} + \varepsilon_i \quad (3)$$

- y_i is the dependent variable at location i (e.g., urban volume).
- x_{ik} are the independent variables at location i (e.g., population density and other predictors).
- $\beta_0(u_i, v_i)$ is the intercept term that varies by location (u_i, v_i) .
- $\beta_k(u_i, v_i)$ are the regression coefficients for the k -th independent variable that vary by location (u_i, v_i) .
- (u_i, v_i) are the coordinates of location i .
- ε_i is the error term at location i .

To achieve accurate results, an adaptive bandwidth was used to ensure that a consistent number of neighboring points were included in each local regression, and a Gaussian kernel function was applied to control the influence of nearby observations. Approximately 31 nearest neighbors were used to calibrate the local regression for each given data point. The local regression was performed at each data point to capture the spatial variability in the relationship between urban volume and

population density.

GWR is highly sensitive to the variables included in the model. Without proper control variables, the model may overfit the data, especially if the number of variables is small relative to the number of observations. Overfitting can lead to poor generalization and misleading conclusions about spatial processes. To address this, partial correlation test (Pingouin Library, Python) tests were used to analyze the relationship between urban volume and population density, accounting for control variables.

2.3.4. XGBoost and SHAP

This study analyzes urban volume growth in Tehran's metropolitan area over four distinct phases: 1985–1995 (Phase I), 1995–2005 (Phase II), 2005–2015 (Phase III), and 2015–2024 (Phase IV). Using XGBoost (Extreme Gradient Boosting), a powerful machine learning algorithm for predicting and identifying complex relationships within large datasets. XGBoost builds an ensemble of decision trees, where each new tree aims to correct the errors of the previous one. This technique helps model the intricate dynamics of urban growth and its factors across time (Xu et al., 2024).

The dependent variable in this analysis is urban volume, which represents the 3D density of built-up areas. The explanatory variables include key spatial, demographic, and economic factors: population density, distance to rail, distance to roads, distance to cities, elevation, employment rate, land value, and GDP. These variables were chosen based on their relevance to urban growth processes and theoretical frameworks in urban planning.

Before applying the XGBoost model, we performed several essential preprocessing steps to ensure data quality. Missing values were imputed, and continuous variables (e.g., population density and land value) were standardized to allow comparability among features. We also conducted a multicollinearity test by calculating the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) to detect highly correlated predictors. A high VIF value (greater than 5) suggests potential multicollinearity, and such variables were either removed or combined to avoid redundancy and ensure stable model performance. Additionally, we examined the correlation among the variables by generating a correlation heatmap. This heatmap visualized pairwise relationships and highlighted variables that were strongly correlated, further aiding in identifying which predictors might require adjustment or removal.

The dataset was then split into training and testing sets. We used an 80–20 train-test split, where 80 % of the data was used for model training and 20 % for model evaluation. The training set was used to train the XGBoost model, while the testing set was reserved for evaluating the model's performance. We employed random sampling to ensure that the train-test split represented the full range of data variations, thereby preventing biases in model evaluation. For model training, we used default parameters for XGBoost, including a maximum tree depth of 6, a learning rate of 0.1, and 100 boosting rounds, ensuring effective learning without overfitting. The model's performance was evaluated using Mean Squared Error (MSE), which quantifies the difference between predicted and actual values.

Considering the method of Novotný et al. (2022) in modeling urban expansion patterns, we also tested the impact of previously established urban volume as a control variable, acknowledging its potential effect on future growth. This is referred to as the 'agglomeration effect,' which accounts for the energy of the already existing urban mass, influencing the tendency for new built-up areas to attach to these already developed zones. The results revealed that the existing urban volume had a significant influence on urban volume growth (Table 1), confirming its pivotal role in shaping urban expansion. Consequently, we included it as a key predictor in our XGBoost model to better capture the patterns of urban growth.

Table 1
XGBoost performance considering pre-existing volume effect as control variable.

Variables	Growth Phase			
	1985–1995	1995–2005	2005–2015	2015–2024
R-Square (With control variable)	0.60	0.65	0.64	0.77
R-Square (Without control variable)	0.22	0.40	0.30	0.28

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{NewVolume} = & \text{PreviousVolume}(\text{agglomerationeffect}) + \beta_1 \\
 & \times \text{PopulationDensity} + \beta_2 \times \text{GDP} + \beta_3 \times \text{EmploymentRate} + \beta_4 \\
 & \times \text{Elevation} + \beta_5 \times \text{LandValue} + \beta_6 \times \text{DistancetoRail} + \beta_7 \\
 & \times \text{DistancetoRoads} + \beta_8 \times \text{DistancetoCities} + \epsilon
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4}$$

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_8$, are the coefficients (weights) that represent the contribution of each variable to the predicted urban volume growth. ϵ represents the residual error, though in XGBoost, this would typically be distributed through the trees' predictions.

Finally, to interpret the model's predictions and understand the importance of each feature, we used SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations). SHAP values, derived from cooperative game theory, explain the contribution of each feature to the model's output. This technique allowed us to identify and visualize the most influential factors in driving urban volume growth in Tehran over time.

Table 2
Incremental growth of population, area, and volume from 1985 to 2024 for each segment.

Segments	Indexes	Time periods				
		1985	1995	2005	2015	2024
S-1985	Population	8150,276	9506,883	9948,195	11,148,117	12,778,781
	Area (km ²)	822.9	822.9	822.9	822.9	822.9
	Volume (km ³)	26,054.0	29,388.4	32,478.5	34,767.6	35,622.0
	V/A (m)	31.7	35.7	39.5	42.3	43.3
	P/A	9904.5	11,553.0	12,089.3	13,547.5	15,529.1
	P/V	312.8	323.5	306.3	320.6	358.7
	S-1995	Population		703,440	875,653	1071,359
	Area (km ²)		141.4	141.4	141.4	141.4
	Volume (km ³)		1553.7	2204.3	2986.1	3157.2
	V/A (m)		11.0	15.6	21.1	22.3
	P/A		4975.9	6194.0	7578.4	8403.9
	P/V		452.8	397.2	358.8	376.3
S-2005	Population			863,577	1240,592	1430,233
	Area (km ²)			142.3	142.3	142.3
	Volume (km ³)			2204.3	3757.9	4104.3
	V/A (m)			15.5	26.4	28.8
	P/A			6067.4	8716.3	10,048.7
	P/V			391.8	330.1	348.5
	S-2015	Population				459,624
	Area (km ²)				342.17	342.17
	Volume (km ³)				1194.3	1398.3
	V/A (m)				3.5	4.1
	P/A				1343.3	1568.8
	P/V				384.8	383.9
S-2024	Population					309,061
	Area (km ²)					528.09
	Volume (km ³)					1171.9
	V/A (m)					2.2
	P/A					585.2
	P/V					263.7
	TMR	Population	8150,276	10,210,323	11,687,425	13,919,691
	Area (km ²)	822.9	964.3	1106.6	1448.8	1976.9
	Volume (km ³)	26,054.0	30,942.1	36,887.1	42,705.9	45,453.7
	V/A (m)	31.7	46.7	70.5	93.3	100.8
	P/A	9904.5	16,528.9	24,350.8	31,185.5	36,135.8
	P/V	312.8	776.2	1095.3	1394.4	1731.1

3. Results

3.1. TMR volumetric growth patterns

The TMR has experienced significant growth in terms of physical (area and volume) and demographical (population) from 1985 to 2024. Each of these dimensions has expanded over time, although the growth patterns differ. Table 2 shows that while the TMR has experienced significant growth in all indices, population and area growing faster than volume, particularly during 2015–2024. The V/A ratio increased from 31.4 to 100.8, indicating densification; however, the slower volume growth suggests that horizontal expansion has outpaced vertical densification in recent years. While P/A and P/V have increased, reflecting improved land-use efficiency, P/V growth rates have slowed during 2015–2024, highlighting a shift toward horizontal sprawl over vertical intensification. The trend suggests that the city has been expanding its footprint extensively, incorporating more land into its urban boundaries rather than focusing on high-density vertical development. noted the predominance of linear and edge expansion due to factors such as proximity to major roads and topographical features, aligning with the observed sprawl. Moreover, the growth in the vicinity of Tehran city has taken on diverse manifestations, such as the enlargement of neighboring cities, the transformation of villages into urban areas, and the establishment of new urban hubs. This has resulted in swift development in the region and the emergence of a burgeoning urban agglomeration (Shafizadeh-Moghadam et al., 2021).

While the aggregate results offer valuable insights into regional trends, a more nuanced understanding of the experiences, contributions, and evolving dynamics of individual sub-regions is crucial for a comprehensive analysis. The S-1984, representing the older areas of the

TMR, exhibited significant vertical growth between 1985 and 2005, as reflected in the V/A ratio. However, this growth markedly slowed during the 2015–2024 period, indicating a deceleration in the segment’s development in recent years. Similar trends are evident in the P/A and P/V ratios. While the P/A ratio nearly doubled over the study period, the P/V ratio showed only marginal increases, highlighting a decline in vertical densification during the 2015–2024 period.

In the S-1995, while the V/A and P/A ratios show upward trends, suggesting densification, the P/A ratio exhibits a downward trend. This indicates that the segment experienced significant vertical growth and absorbed the expansion from the S-1985 by increasing land-use efficiency. In S-2005, a similar trend is observed, with greater vertical growth compared to S-1995, as indicated by the increases in both the V/A and P/V ratios. However, in the subsequent S-2015 and S-2024, the trend reversed. In S-2015, although the area increased substantially compared to the S-2005 and S-1995 segments, the V/A, P/A, and P/V ratios show that the segment accommodated fewer people in a larger, less dense area, suggesting significant horizontal expansion and sprawl. In S-2024, despite considerable area growth compared to previous segments, the V/A ratio and population indicators indicates a sparse population distribution across a low-density, low-rise development, suggesting that the region’s growth has not maintained efficient land use, resulting in extensive urban sprawl in the TMR.

The analysis of built volume changes in the TMR over four phases (1985–1995, 1995–2005, 2005–2015, and 2015–2024) reveals a significant evolution in urban expansion patterns, particularly in the balance between vertical densification and horizontal sprawl (Fig. 4). During the first phase (1985–1995), TMR built-up volume increased by 18 %, with S-1985 vertical densification (68.3 %) serving as the primary driver, concentrated within the established urban core. However, horizontal expansion accounted for 31.7 % of the growth, indicating the initial stages of outward urban development in S-1995. In the second phase (1995–2005), the TMR volume increased to 19 %, with vertical densification continuing in the older urban segments of S-1985 and S-1995. Concurrently, horizontal expansion became more pronounced (37 %), particularly in the newly developed areas of S-2005 that contributed to the expansion of the metropolitan footprint. By the third phase (2005–2015), the growth rate of TMR volume declined to 15.7 %,

marking a transition toward moderate saturation in vertical development. In this phase the vertical densification remained a significant component of urban growth and signifies the high stages of densification through UVG.

The most recent phase (2015–2024) represents a critical shift in the region’s urban development trajectory. The total growth rate dropped to 6 %, the lowest among all phases. Unlike previous periods, where vertical expansion dominated, horizontal growth (42.6 %) in the S-2024 emerged as the principal mode of development. Although vertical densification persisted in earlier segments, its overall contribution declined, reflecting a marked transition toward extensive suburban expansion and low-density sprawl. Three key insights emerge from this longitudinal analysis. First, the overall rate of built volume growth has progressively declined, likely due to land-use constraints, economic factors, or policy-driven limitations on urban development. Second, the 1985 segment, representing the historical urban core, has consistently played a central role in vertical expansion, highlighting its enduring significance in the region’s urban densification. Finally, the shift from vertical densification to horizontal sprawl, particularly in the most recent phase, underscores the challenges associated with unchecked suburbanization. This transition raises concerns regarding long-term sustainability, necessitating strategic urban planning interventions to balance growth while mitigating the adverse effects of sprawl on land use, infrastructure, and transportation systems.

3.2. Spatiotemporal heterogeneity analysis

Table 3 analyzes spatial autocorrelation for population and urban volume from 1985 to 2024 using Moran’s I and LISA. Moran’s I values for both variables indicate positively auto-correlated and a consistently high degree of spatial clustering, with Population’s Moran’s I hovering around 0.8 and urban volume increasing from 0.64 to 0.77 over time. This suggests that population and urban volume have increasingly clustered patterns, indicating that urban development has become increasingly concentrated in specific regions. The consistent P-values of 0.001 confirm that these spatial patterns are statistically significant, reflecting persistent population clustering and growing concentration in urban development.

Fig. 4. overall and segmental growth change of TMR in four phases. V stands for vertical densification, H stands for horizontal emergence.

Table 3
The results of global Moran I and LISA.

		Moran's I	LISA				
			Not-significant	low-low	low-high	high-low	high-high
Population	1985	0.82	63.91 %	26.03 %	0.39 %	0.07 %	9.60 %
	1995	0.83	61.88 %	26.22 %	0.50 %	0.09 %	11.31 %
	2005	0.79	54.67 %	27.24 %	0.87 %	0.11 %	17.11 %
	2015	0.81	53.11 %	29.85 %	0.69 %	0.04 %	16.32 %
	2024	0.80	48.40 %	31.85 %	0.79 %	0.04 %	18.92 %
Urban volume	1985	0.64	58.56 %	19.31 %	1.82 %	0.56 %	19.74 %
	1995	0.68	54.98 %	21.96 %	1.64 %	0.50 %	20.91 %
	2005	0.71	53.22 %	23.59 %	1.40 %	0.28 %	21.51 %
	2015	0.74	50.73 %	25.05 %	1.21 %	0.16 %	22.84 %
	2024	0.77	46.15 %	28.67 %	1.04 %	0.10 %	24.05 %

According to the summary counts of counties by LISA categories reported in Figs. 5 and 6, over the years, the percentage of areas with no significant local spatial autocorrelation (Not-significant) decreased for both variables, while the percentage of areas classified as Low-Low (clusters of low values) and High-High (clusters of high values) grows.

For Population, High-High clusters increase from 9.60 % to 18.92 %, indicating greater concentration in densely populated regions, while Low-Low clusters rise from 26.03 % to 31.85 %, reflecting spatial clustering of low-population areas. Similarly, Urban volume increases in High-High clusters from 19.74 % to 24.05 % and in Low-Low clusters

Fig. 5. LISA spatial autocorrelation results of population distribution in TMR.

Fig. 6. LISA spatial autocorrelation results of built-up volume distribution in TMR.

from 19.31 % to 28.67 %, indicating intensified clustering of both high and low urban development areas. Overall, the results point to growing spatial inequalities, with high-density and low-density areas becoming more spatially distinct over time.

Fig. 7 illustrates the spatial regression GWR between population density and the urban volume in the TMR from 1985 to 2024. The data is represented using standardized residuals, indicating the discrepancies between observed and predicted values over different years. In 1985, the map revealed that most areas exhibit residuals within the -0.5 to 0.5 standard deviation range, suggesting a moderate correlation between population density and urban volume. By 1995, a significant increase in areas with residuals of -2.5 to -1.5 and 1.5 to 2.5 standard deviations was observed, particularly around Tehran, indicating greater variability and a possible shift in urban development patterns. This trend intensifies by 2005, with more pronounced clusters of high residuals (>2.5 standard deviations) and low residuals (<-2.5 standard deviations), highlighting emerging disparities in urban growth and population distribution. The 2015 map continues this trend, showing expansive areas with high positive residuals around Tehran city, suggesting rapid

urbanization exceeding the predicted models, while some peripheral regions show high negative residuals, indicating less development than anticipated. The 2024 maps exacerbate these patterns, reflecting continued urban sprawl and intensified divergence from the regression model, particularly around the metropolitan core (Tehran city). Overall, the progression over these four decades underscores a dynamic and increasingly complex relationship between population density and urban development, driven by significant socio-economic and infrastructural changes in the TMR. The increasing spread of high and low residuals suggests a need for revised urban planning strategies to effectively manage the disparities in development.

Table 4 shows that a strong positive correlation between population density and urban volume in the TMR, even when controlling for other potential influencing factors. This suggests that the relationship between these two variables is robust and likely reflects a genuine association. As the region continues to urbanize, the relationship between population density and urban volume is expected to become even stronger. The Goodness of fit of GWR analysis is also reported in Table 4. Accordingly, adjusted R^2 values are consistently high, ranging from 0.611 in 1995 to

Fig. 7. spatial regression GWR between population density and the urban volume in TMR.

Table 4
The correlation between population density and urban volume with/without control variables.

Year	without control variables		with control variables		goodness of fit of GWR	
	R	P-value	R	P-value	Moran' I	AdjustedR2
1985	0.307	0.000	0.336	0.000	-0.002	0.686
1995	0.362	0.000	0.383	0.000	0.004	0.611
2005	0.599	0.000	0.592	0.000	0.015	0.706
2015	0.608	0.000	0.586	0.000	0.030	0.729
2024	0.667	0.000	0.642	0.000	0.033	0.748

0.748 in 2024, showing that the model effectively captures the variance in built-up volume based on population density alone. Moran's I values for the model residuals are nearly zero across all years, suggesting

minimal spatial autocorrelation. low Moran's I value, and high adjusted R² demonstrate that the model is neither substantially overfitting nor underfitting the data and remains robust through multiple time points.

3.3. Driving factors analysis

We analyzed multicollinearity before running the XGBoost model to evaluate the relationships between key predictors across four temporal phases (1985–1995, 1995–2005, 2005–2015, and 2015–2024) in Fig. 8. The correlation analysis did not reveal major multicollinearity issues, as no strong linear dependencies were observed among the predictors. While some moderate correlations exist, particularly between population, employment, and built-up volume, they are not high enough to significantly impact model performance. These findings suggest that all variables can be retained in the XGBoost model without the need for extensive feature selection or dimensionality reduction.

Fig. 8. Correlation heatmap of independent variables.

In addition, The VIF results further confirm the absence of severe multicollinearity in Table 5. Across all phases, the VIF values remain well below the commonly used threshold of 10, indicating that no predictor exhibits a high degree of linear dependency with others. The highest VIF values were observed for Population (2.74), Employment (2.29), and Built-Up Volume (2.01) in some periods, but these remain within an acceptable range. Additionally, distance-related and elevation variables consistently showed low VIF values, reinforcing their independence within the dataset. Given these results, no variables require removal, and all predictors can be included in the XGBoost model without concerns about multicollinearity affecting model performance.

The results of the XGBoost and SHAP value to assess the relative influence of each predictor on urban expansion and feature importance

Table 5
VIF Analysis of independent variables.

Variables	1985-1995	1995-2005	2005-2015	2015-2024
Population density	1.78	2.57	2.24	2.74
Pre-existing volume	1.63	2.01	1.32	1.29
Dis_rail	1.30	1.25	1.42	1.28
Dis_road	1.07	1.17	1.06	1.27
Dis_cities	1.07	1.03	1.03	1.06
Elevation	1.16	1.10	1.13	1.35
Employment rate	1.62	2.29	2.22	2.21
Landvalue	1.08	1.04	1.06	1.54
GDP	1.39	1.60	1.40	1.54

in Fig. 9 reveal significant distinctions between the first two phases (1985-1995 and 1995-2005) and the latter two phases (2005-2015 and 2015-2024).

Phase I (1985-1995): The Dominance of Historical Built-Up Areas

The SHAP value analysis for Phase I indicates that pre-existing built-up volume of S-1985 played a dominant role in determining urban expansion patterns. Areas with lower initial built-up volume exhibited a strong positive correlation with the emergence of high-density urban zones, suggesting that urban growth predominantly occurred in locations that had previously been less developed. This highlights the role of spatial inertia, where expansion builds upon pre-existing urban structures. Population density emerged as the second most important factor, displaying a distinct pattern in the SHAP plots. Low population levels were associated with lower urban volume expansion, while high population densities exhibited a strong positive relationship with high-volume urban development. This suggests that population growth was a major driver of densification, as people tended to settle in already developed, high-density areas rather than expanding into new, low-density regions. Elevation also played a critical role, indicating that higher-altitude areas were more likely to experience urban expansion compared to lower-elevation zones. This suggests that urban growth was somewhat constrained by topographical features, favoring higher terrains for development. Additional spatial factors such as proximity to major cities and railway networks further influenced urban growth.

Fig. 9. XGBoost feature importance of driving factors of urban volume growth and SHAP values of local impact on model output.

Higher-volume urban areas were more likely to emerge near these transport infrastructures, whereas lower-density areas were more commonly found at greater distances. Employment levels and land value also played a notable role, as higher employment concentrations and elevated land values were strongly aligned with higher urban volumes, reinforcing the economic motivations for urban expansion.

Phase II (1995–2005): Strengthened Trends and Emerging Infrastructure Influence

In this phase, areas with lower prior built-up volume exhibited a stronger association with high -volume new urban development, further reinforcing the trend of expansion occurring in previously underdeveloped areas which had low volume. However, the effect of high population density shows strong positive consistent with high volume of new built-ups, and Vic versa the strong consistent of low population density with low volume developments. A notable shift in this phase was the increasing significance of proximity to roads, which emerged as a more influential factor than in the previous phase. The SHAP values indicate that high urban volumes were more likely to develop in areas located farther from major roads, suggesting a decentralization trend where urban growth extended beyond core transportation corridors. However, proximity to cities continued to exert a strong influence, with high urban

volumes forming in areas closer to major urban centers. As distance from cities increased, the likelihood of high-volume urban expansion decreased, reinforcing the notion that urban agglomerations remained central to development patterns. Economic factors, including land value, had a relatively smaller influence in this phase compared to spatial and demographic variables. This suggests that while economic conditions played a role, urban expansion during this period was primarily dictated by population growth, pre-existing built-up conditions, and infrastructure accessibility. The declining importance of GDP and Employment indicates that economic growth, though relevant, did not strongly dictate spatial development patterns during this period. Overall, these findings highlight a transition from purely spatial inertia-driven growth in Phase I to a more infrastructure-responsive expansion pattern in Phase II. The increasing role of road networks and accessibility suggests a growing emphasis on connectivity in shaping urban form, setting the stage for the evolving urban dynamics observed in later phases.

Phase III (2005–2015): The Shift Towards Population Growth

This phase marked a significant shift in the drivers of urban expansion, with Population surpassing existing built-up volume as the most influential factor. This transition indicates that demographic pressures, including migration, urban densification, and housing demand, became

the primary force behind urbanization. Unlike previous phases, where new development often occurred in areas with lower initial built-up volumes, this period saw a reversal: high values of pre-existing urban volume were now associated with high values of new urban volume. This suggests that urban densification, particularly through vertical growth, became a dominant mode of expansion within already developed areas. Older urban segments became more densely built, while newer segments emerged in areas with initially low urban volume, leading to a dual pattern of intensification and expansion. Elevation remained a crucial determinant of urban expansion, reinforcing the idea that geographical constraints continued to shape growth patterns. Meanwhile, rail accessibility (*Dis_rail*) gained prominence, suggesting that proximity to rail infrastructure became an increasingly important factor in guiding spatial development. This could reflect the role of transit-oriented development, where areas well-served by rail networks became more attractive for urban growth due to enhanced connectivity and accessibility. The impact of Land Value also intensified compared to previous phases, indicating that economic considerations played a more significant role in shaping urban expansion trends. The consistent negative relationship between high land values and new urban volumes suggests that expensive land acted as a barrier to large-scale development. High land costs may have discouraged new construction, potentially due to speculative landholding, restrictive zoning policies, or affordability constraints that limited large-scale residential or commercial expansion. Conversely, areas with lower land values likely facilitated more substantial urban growth, as they provided economically viable opportunities for development. This trend underscores the increasing influence of market forces in directing urban expansion, with economic accessibility becoming a key determinant of where and how cities grow.

Phase IV (2015–2024): Economic and Spatial Constraints Intensify

In the most recent phase, Population and Volume₂₀₁₅ remained the dominant predictor, reaffirming that demographic expansion is the leading force in urban growth. However, unlike previous phases, Elevation reversed its impact, with lower elevations now being consistently associated with higher new urban volumes. This could indicate a saturation of developable land at higher elevations, pushing new developments toward flatter, lower-lying regions. Means Land Value exhibited sustained high importance, highlighting the increasing impact of land-market dynamics on urban expansion decisions. The relationship between land value and urban volume exhibited a dual pattern, as high land values were observed in both low and high urban volume areas. This suggests that land value does not have a strictly linear relationship with urban expansion. Instead, it reflects two contrasting dynamics: (1) in established high-density urban centers, high land values correspond with significant urban growth due to increased demand and investment, and (2) in less developed peripheral areas, speculative land pricing or restrictive policies may lead to high land values despite low urban expansion. The continued significance of *Dis_rail* and *Dis_cities* suggests that accessibility to transport infrastructure remains a key determinant of urban expansion. Interestingly, GDP and Employment had the lowest impact in this phase, indicating that while economic conditions may shape urbanization patterns, they are secondary to population-driven and spatial constraints.

4. Discussion

4.1. Discussion of findings

Urbanization in high-density metropolitan regions follows a dual trajectory, encompassing both horizontal expansion and vertical densification. This shift highlights the necessity of a three-dimensional approach to urban planning, where vertical growth is recognized as a fundamental component of sustainable urban development alongside traditional horizontal expansion. While much of the existing literature

has predominantly examined urbanization through the lens of horizontal sprawl, our study advances this discourse by adopting a volumetric perspective, capturing the interplay between outward and upward growth. Using Tehran—a rapidly expanding metropolitan region in the Global South—as a case study, we investigate macro-level patterns of volumetric growth and microlevel intra-urban variations, also the underlying drivers of volumetric growth of TMR.

Between 1985 and 2024, urban expansion in the TMR has undergone four distinct phases, each marked by varying patterns of horizontal and vertical growth. In the first two phases, urban expansion followed a relatively balanced trajectory, with both horizontal sprawl and vertical densification contributing to a more compact urban form. However, in the third phase, a clear divergence emerged: while the urban core experienced increasing density, low-density suburban developments began to spread outward. The most recent phase has been characterized by a dual pattern—intensified densification in central areas accompanied by extensive suburban sprawl. This shift marks a transition from a compact, high-density urban model toward a more dispersed pattern of development, where outward expansion has surpassed vertical intensification as the dominant form of growth. A key indicator of this transformation is the decoupling of volumetric urban expansion from population density. While the built environment has continued to expand, the decline in population per unit of urban volume suggests a shift away from compact, high-density forms toward lower-density, spatially dispersed urbanization. This trend has been particularly pronounced over the past decade, signaling a fundamental departure from earlier growth trajectories. This pattern aligns with cities in the Global South (Chakraborty et al., 2022; Novotný et al., 2022) continue to experience rapid outward expansion (Chakraborty et al., 2021), fueled by high population growth, weak planning regulations, and unregulated land markets, exacerbating urban sprawl, inefficient land use, and infrastructure deficits (Jedwab et al., 2021).

However, segmental analysis findings indicates that there is distinct intra-urban variation bet different segments of TMR in four phases of analyzes. the historical urban core (S-1985) has stood out as a consistent hub of vertical densification. Unlike the broader region, this area has maintained its focus on upward growth, with taller buildings and higher population densities. This trend of vertical densification of later segments of 1995, 2005, and 2015 through act like wave decline, which means the city attempt to keep compactness. These results suggest while older regions continue to densify at a reduced pace, a shift in urban development within the TMR, with newer areas becoming the focus of growth. The urban renewal projects in the older city cores have led to permissions for constructing and replacing high-rise buildings instead of old structures. This policy has generally resulted in increased building density in the historical centers of most Iranian cities. However, more recently, the findings highlight a pivot to horizontal sprawl, especially evident in S-2024. This shift signals the beginning of a new phase of suburban dominance, where growth is increasingly concentrated in suburban areas rather than the urban core. It has served as a cornerstone of TMR's urban identity, preserving a model of compact, high-density development even as the surrounding region sprawled outward.

We found that pattern of vertical densification of TMR consist with diffusion-coalescence theory in horizontal (2D) urban expansion studies (Chakraborty et al., 2021; Dietzel et al., 2005). Prior studies have identified three distinct stages in this process: the initial development of the city core, a subsequent diffusion phase, and finally, a coalescence stage. This sequential progression follows the tidal wave model of urban expansion, where peak growth moves outward in successive waves as development saturates one concentric zone and shifts to the next (Chakraborty, Dadashpoor, et al., 2022; Chakraborty et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2020 Alaei Moghadam et al., 2018). This phenomenon reflects a cyclical interaction between centralization and decentralization, driving urban expansion over different time intervals (Hajjar et al., 2023; Xu et al., 2019, Dehghani et al., 2023; Moghadam et al., 2018a; Moghadam, Soltani, & Parolin, 2018b). The study of Novotný et al. (2022)analyzing

43 worlds megacities including TMR, reported macro-patterns of urban expansion by their simultaneous presence accompanied by the gradual shifts in their intensities in the sequence from outlying through edge expansion to infilling. In case of TMR, they found that outlying and edge expansion is the most predominant types drive its spatial extents. This finding is more aligned with results of our study specifically the recent expansion of TMR in phase 2015–2024 where we found low volume and large extent expansion.

The findings of our study highlight the critical role of pre-existing urban mass in shaping the expansion trajectory of the TMR, where both horizontal growth and vertical densification have been influenced by the volume of existing built-up areas. This aligns with the agglomeration effect observed in urban expansion studies, where established urban centers attract further growth due to accumulated infrastructure, economic activity, and social networks (Li et al., 2022; Novotný et al., 2022). In TMR, horizontal expansion remains anchored to pre-existing developed zones rather than forming isolated centers, while vertical densification has become increasingly prominent, particularly in areas with high initial built-up volume. Our SHAP analysis suggests that such areas are more likely to experience intensified vertical expansion, reflecting how housing demand, land scarcity, and regulatory frameworks collectively shape high-density development. These dynamics are consistent with urbanization trends in the Global South, particularly in rapidly growing Asian megacities. Studies on urban expansion in China (Kong et al., 2022) have shown that early phases of horizontal growth often transition toward vertical densification as land-use constraints intensify, a pattern also observed in Shanghai, Beijing, and Mumbai (Zhou et al., 2021). Similarly, Chakraborty, Dadashpoor, et al. (2022) emphasized that as megacities approach land saturation, densification becomes the dominant growth mode—a trend now evident in TMR. These parallels suggest that TMR's urban transformation aligns with broader global patterns, reinforcing the necessity of volumetric analyses to fully capture the complexities of contemporary urbanization.

Drivers of Urban expansion in the TMR follows a global urbanization trajectory, transitioning from spatial inertia, Emerging Infrastructure Influence, to population-driven growth and, more recently, to constraints imposed by economic and geographic factors (Carlucci et al., 2020; Henderson & Turner, 2020; Jedwab et al., 2021). The evolution of urban expansion in the TMR has followed distinct phases, each shaped by different underlying drivers. While the patterns align with global urbanization trends, the defining themes of each phase emerge from a combination of historical conditions, infrastructure development, demographic shifts, economic forces, and policy decisions. In the first phase (1985–1995), urban expansion was primarily dictated by spatial inertia, meaning that historical settlement structures and pre-existing urban cores shaped the trajectory of growth. The city expanded outward incrementally, following existing road networks, topographical constraints, and pre-industrial urban forms. This pattern resembled early expansion phases in cities such as Istanbul or Cairo, where organic growth extended from historical cores due to economic centralization and limited infrastructure investment. During this period, there was little large-scale urban planning, and growth was largely an extension of past urban structures. The second phase (1995–2005) marked the increasing influence of infrastructure development as a driver of expansion. Investments in roads, public transit, and utilities played a crucial role in shaping urban growth. The construction of highways, metro lines, and satellite cities made peripheral areas more accessible, encouraging outward expansion. This phase saw the early signs of suburbanization, as middle-class populations began moving into newly developed areas outside the city center (Bagheri & Soltani, 2023). Similar patterns were observed in cities like Jakarta and Bangkok, where large-scale transportation projects spurred rapid suburban growth, often outpacing regulatory controls (Frolking et al., 2022; Sarker et al., 2024).

During the third phase (2005–2015), demographic pressures and housing demand became the dominant forces driving expansion. Rapid population growth, combined with increased rural-to-urban migration,

created a pressing need for large-scale housing developments. This led to a dual expansion pattern: some areas experienced densification through mid-rise and high-rise construction, while others underwent unplanned suburban sprawl. As urbanization progressed, population growth became the dominant force, driving both outward expansion and increased density in urban cores, a trend common in Global South cities where rapid demographic shifts initially expand peripheries before densification intensifies due to land constraints (Wang et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2019, Azhdari et al., 2018a). A comparable trend was observed in cities like São Paulo and Mumbai, where high-density urban cores coexisted with informal settlements on the periphery (Denis, 2020; Gambe et al., 2023; Huang & Xu, 2022). However, in TMR, government policies played a major role in shaping these outcomes. Since the 1960s, the issue of affordable housing has posed a major obstacle to Iran's economic and social development initiatives. This is primarily due to causes such as the country's integration into the capitalist world, expansion of industrial activities, implementation of land reforms, and the migration of people from rural to urban areas (Ghaedrahmati & Zarghamfard, 2021). These events have resulted in housing shortages and the proliferation of slums, particularly in large metropolitan areas like TMR (Janakipour et al., 2022; Rajaei & Mansourian, 2016). Beginning in 2005, a decline in the housing sector led the government to decrease mortgage rates to boost demand, resulting in a subsequent rise in property prices. The Mehr Housing Plan implemented in 2007, sought to ensure sufficient housing for low-income populations by employing tactics such as the gratuitous allocation of government-owned land and regulating residential property prices, particularly in urban centers. Consequently, many government lands were rapidly developed, often without prior urban and regional planning, which led to a more horizontal with less population density growth pattern in TMR (Zanganeh Shahraki et al., 2020; Moghadam et al., 2018a).

In the most recent phase (2015–2024), economic and geographic constraints have emerged as the primary forces shaping urban growth. Rising land prices have led to two contrasting trends: vertical intensification in central areas and low-density suburbanization in more affordable peripheral zones. This has resulted in a paradox where both high urban volumes and low-density developments coexist, similar to patterns seen in megacities like Kolkata (Bhatta, 2009; Chakraborty et al., 2021). Unlike earlier phases where growth was primarily demand-driven, the latest phase is shaped by market forces, policy limitations, and environmental constraints, such as restricted land availability due to mountains and protected areas. The decline in population density per unit of urban volume suggests that while the built environment continues to expand, the distribution of residents has become more dispersed—signaling a shift away from compact urban forms. One of the primary drivers of vertical growth is the economic imperative to maximize land use efficiency. In high-density urban cores, increasing land values encourage developers to construct high-rise buildings, intensifying land use to accommodate demand. This aligns with classical urban economic theories, such as bid-rent theory, which explains how competition for land influences building height variations. However, the presence of high land values in low-density peripheral areas complicates this model. In some cases, speculative investment or restrictive planning policies may inflate land prices without translating into urban growth, delaying densification.

Previous studies primarily categorize urban expansion into the sequential co-occurrence of three growth types: outlying expansion and edge expansion, which represent horizontal spread, and infill development, which reflects horizontal densification. However, these frameworks overlook vertical growth, failing to fully capture the complexity of urban expansion. Our findings suggest that while vertical densification often follows horizontal expansion, it can also emerge concurrently with these growth patterns. Specifically, as older, established segments continue to densify vertically in response to land scarcity, newly developed segments exhibit distinct volumetric characteristics. This nuanced dynamic can only be effectively analyzed through a volumetric

approach, which accounts for both the horizontal and vertical dimensions of urban growth. A volumetric perspective overcomes the limitations of conventional horizontal analyses by providing deeper insights into intra-urban variations and the differing trajectories of mature and newly emerging urban segments (Soltani et al., 2025b). First, our results indicate that older urban segments in TMR, such as S-1995, initially developed with higher built-up volumes, whereas newer segments emerged with lower volumetric density. This suggests that early urbanization was characterized by more intensive vertical expansion, while recent developments have prioritized horizontal spread. Second, volumetric metrics effectively capture the densification trends in older urban cores, where the scarcity of available land has driven upward expansion. In these mature segments, vertical growth compensates for spatial constraints, leading to increased built-up volume despite minimal horizontal expansion. Third, the volumetric approach highlights the simultaneous processes of densification in older urban cores and expansion in peripheral areas. This co-occurrence underscores the multi-directional nature of urbanization, where compact growth and sprawl operate in tandem rather than in isolation. By integrating vertical growth into urban expansion analysis, our study provides a more comprehensive understanding of urban transformation, challenging the prevailing emphasis on two-dimensional growth models.

4.2. Sustainability challenges and policy pathways

The dual trajectory of vertical densification and horizontal expansion reveals diverging implications for sustainability, resilience, and livability. Vertical densification is often promoted as a sustainable urban form due to its potential to reduce land consumption, enable efficient infrastructure use, support public transportation, and limit encroachment on natural and agricultural land. High-density development can lower per capita energy consumption, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and create more walkable, transit-accessible communities. However, the sustainability benefits of vertical growth are highly dependent on the capacity of urban systems to absorb added density. In the case of TMR, particularly in the historic core, rapid vertical expansion has outpaced the modernization of essential infrastructure. Aging water, energy, and sewage networks, which were designed for lower-density use, have become overstressed, leading to frequent service disruptions and operational inefficiencies. These challenges are further compounded by Tehran's location in a high seismic hazard zone, intersected by active faults such as the North Tehran and Mosha faults. The concentration of population in high-rise buildings without adequate retrofitting or compliance with seismic codes significantly increases disaster vulnerability. To realize the sustainability potential of vertical growth while mitigating its risks, Tehran must implement a multi-pronged policy strategy: (1) restrict high-rise development in seismically sensitive areas using updated micro-zonation maps; (2) mandate retrofitting of existing vulnerable structures through targeted subsidies or development incentives; and while retrofitting is a critical immediate step to address existing vulnerabilities, particularly in seismically active zones, it should be strategically aligned with a long-term urban vision, serving in some areas as a permanent solution and in others as a transitional measure for more comprehensive, resilient redevelopment; and (3) tie vertical development approvals to demonstrated infrastructure readiness, including capacity thresholds for utilities and mobility systems. Cities like Singapore and Vienna have demonstrated how high-density development can support lower emissions and resilient urban living when aligned with infrastructure capacity and risk-sensitive planning.

Beyond structural vulnerabilities, vertical densification also intensifies environmental stress, particularly by amplifying the urban heat island (UHI) effect. These patterns reflect broader findings, such as Chen et al. (2024), who identify a strong correlation between vertical density and UHI intensity in rapidly urbanizing Chinese cities. In Tehran's dense districts, such as 21 and 22, widespread vegetation loss, impervious

surfaces, and poor ventilation have contributed to elevated surface temperatures and increased cooling energy demand (Ghanbari et al., 2023). High-rise development can undermine sustainability by reducing thermal comfort and air quality without ecological integration. Beyond UHI and seismic risks, the sustainability of TMR's growth model is also challenged by broader climate change impacts, notably increasing water scarcity and the potential for more frequent and intense heatwaves. Vertical densification, if not coupled with water-efficient infrastructure and design, can further strain limited water resources, while both dense and sprawling forms can exacerbate vulnerability to extreme heat if green and blue infrastructure is inadequate. To address this, Tehran should implement mandatory green roofs and façades, expand urban tree canopy coverage, and preserve ventilation corridors through zoning (Azhdari, Soltani, & Alidadi, 2018b; Tanoori, Soltani, & Modiri, 2024a; Tanoori, Soltani, & Modiri, 2024b; Sharifi & Soltani, 2017). Lessons from Singapore, where green infrastructure is systematically integrated into vertical urban form, demonstrate how climate-responsive design can offset the environmental costs of densification and help avoid the paradox of "unsustainable compactness".

Vertical redevelopment can also generate serious equity challenges when not managed inclusively. This mirrors experiences in cities like Jakarta, where densification without social protections led to widespread exclusion of informal and vulnerable communities (Firman, 2009). In the TMR's older neighborhoods, high-rise construction has often involved the demolition of low-rise and informal housing, displacing lower-income residents who cannot afford the redeveloped units. Many are forced to relocate to peripheral or under-served areas, where housing is cheaper but access to jobs, transit, and public services is limited. This process contributes to spatial inequality, while rising land values and new investment in redeveloped zones accelerate gentrification and erode local social networks. To avoid similar outcomes, TMR densification strategies must incorporate equity-focused tools, including inclusionary zoning, rent stabilization, and tenure security, alongside participatory planning and cultural impact assessments. These measures are essential to ensure that vertical urban growth does not come at the cost of community stability and social cohesion.

Unchecked horizontal expansion across TMR presents equally severe challenges, particularly concerning environmental degradation, infrastructure inefficiency, and spatial inequality. Suburban developments have increasingly sprawled into agricultural lands, natural slopes, and ecologically sensitive zones, fragmenting habitat corridors and threatening regional biodiversity (Dehghani et al., 2025; Ramyar et al., 2025; Soltani et al., 2017). These peripheral areas are often designed with low-density, single-use zoning, resulting in high dependence on private vehicles, longer commutes, and increased per capita greenhouse gas emissions. Similar patterns have been observed in cities such as Cairo and Lahore, where rapid suburbanization, driven by housing demand but unsupported by coordinated planning, has undermined sustainability and livability. In TMR, the expansion of state-subsidized housing schemes into remote areas has created large settlements suffering limited access to schools, healthcare, employment, and efficient public transit. The mismatch between population growth and service provision has led to underutilized developments, rising dissatisfaction among residents, and increased socio-spatial fragmentation. These dynamics reflect broader institutional challenges: planning authorities often lack the regulatory reach or coordination mechanisms to guide suburban growth toward sustainable outcomes. To address this, TMR must move beyond the current pattern of fragmented sprawl and adopt a model of transit-oriented, compact suburban development. This involves prioritizing medium-density, mixed-use neighborhoods anchored by high-capacity transit corridors and integrated service delivery. Land-use regulations should promote walkability, ensure proximity to essential amenities, and prevent development in environmentally sensitive areas. Without such a shift, horizontal expansion will continue to erode environmental assets, exacerbate social inequities, and lock the city into an unsustainable growth trajectory.

A primary structural driver of both speculative vertical construction and outward expansion in TMR is the phenomenon of land banking. Investors frequently hold vacant land in central districts for capital gains, exacerbating housing shortages and diverting development toward cheaper peripheral zones. This speculative behavior distorts land markets and contributes to spatial fragmentation. To counter these dynamics, Tehran should introduce a land value tax (LVT) to disincentivize land hoarding and promote infill development. Cities such as Vienna and Seoul have effectively used LVT to regulate land supply, enhance affordability, and redirect growth toward serviced urban areas. Revenue from such policies can fund infrastructure investments in underdeveloped segments of the metropolitan region. Crucially, the success of such policy interventions hinges on strengthening institutional capacity and fostering inter-municipal coordination across the TMR. This involves not only empowering planning authorities with robust enforcement mechanisms but also building technical expertise, ensuring transparency in decision-making, and cultivating the political will necessary to overcome entrenched interests that benefit from the status quo of speculative and uncoordinated development. Without a coherent governance framework that transcends administrative boundaries and short-term political cycles, even well-designed policies may falter.

TMR's sustainable urban future depends on transitioning toward a polycentric and integrated planning model. Rather than viewing vertical and horizontal expansion as competing forces, the city must align them through coordinated strategies that promote moderate densification in central districts and compact, well-serviced growth in suburban nodes. Enforcing urban growth boundaries, prioritizing infill and brownfield redevelopment, and linking density incentives to infrastructure performance are essential steps. Transit-oriented development (TOD) should guide all future expansion, ensuring accessibility, reduced car dependency, and efficient service delivery. Furthermore, the successful implementation of these transformative strategies—be it densification, sprawl containment, or infrastructure upgrading—requires genuine and sustained public participation. Building social acceptance and co-designing solutions with diverse communities, including long-term residents, newcomers, and marginalized groups, can enhance the legitimacy and effectiveness of urban plans, fostering a sense of collective ownership and mitigating potential social resistance to change. International models such as Hong Kong's vertical TOD framework, Copenhagen's Finger Plan, and London's polycentric structure provide applicable precedents. Adopting a regionally coordinated, resilience-informed spatial strategy for Tehran is critical to balancing growth with infrastructure capacity, environmental limits, and social equity.

The case of the TMR offers valuable insights for other fast-growing cities in the Global South, where rapid urbanization frequently occurs under weak planning enforcement, speculative landholding, and inadequate infrastructure. The region's dual trajectory of vertical densification in central areas and unregulated horizontal sprawl in peripheral zones reflects a broader challenge many metropolitan areas face: how to accommodate population growth without undermining sustainability or resilience. Similar patterns have been observed in Jakarta, Cairo, and Lagos. However, the TMR is particularly notable for the extent to which vertical and horizontal growth have co-occurred, often without alignment with infrastructure capacity or environmental thresholds. This experience highlights the critical importance of achieving "optimal density". This concept refers to a balance where compact urban form enhances energy efficiency, service delivery, and land conservation while remaining within the urban system's social, environmental, and infrastructural limits. Achieving this 'optimal density' is not merely an environmental or social imperative but also an economic one. Well-managed compact development can foster agglomeration economies, innovation, and efficient service delivery, whereas uncontrolled sprawl often leads to higher per capita infrastructure costs, increased transportation expenditures for households, and lost productivity, ultimately undermining regional competitiveness. The TMR illustrates that, if densification is not carefully managed, it can lead to overstressed

infrastructure, intensified urban heat, and the displacement of lower-income populations. Conversely, uncoordinated horizontal expansion contributes to spatial fragmentation, higher carbon emissions, and the degradation of ecological systems. For planners and policymakers in other cities, the key lesson is that volumetric growth should be regulated not only in terms of its scale but also in relation to its spatial configuration and functional performance. Aligning the form of urban development with infrastructure readiness, environmental constraints, and social equity is essential. Incorporating volumetric indicators into urban governance frameworks can support more accurate assessments of growth patterns and their implications. As cities continue to expand vertically and horizontally, managing the form and structure of this growth will be critical to promoting long-term sustainability, resilience, and inclusivity. Therefore, the path towards a sustainable urban future for TMR and similar cities necessitates not only robust initial planning but also a commitment to continuous monitoring, evaluation, and adaptive management. Employing tools like volumetric indicators, geospatial analysis, and regular sustainability assessments can help track the impacts of development policies, allowing for timely adjustments and ensuring that growth trajectories remain aligned with evolving resilience, equity, and environmental goals.

4.3. Research limitations and directions for the future

The main limitation of this study is its exclusive focus on volumetric densification trends, which does not account for other growth patterns such as outlying, edge, and infill development. Future research should integrate these growth modes with the volumetric approach to offer a more comprehensive analysis of urban dynamics, capturing both horizontal sprawl and vertical densification more effectively. This would provide a fuller understanding of the complexities of urban growth in metropolitan regions like Tehran.

The other limitation of this study is the limited number of driving forces analyzed, mainly due to restricted access to reliable time-series data. While we aimed to capture the complexity of urban growth, data constraints, especially for Tehran and Iran, hindered our ability to include certain socioeconomic and environmental variables. As a result, we focused on variables with consistently reliable data, which may not fully reflect the multifaceted nature of urban growth. Future research should aim to incorporate a broader range of driving forces by improving access to comprehensive and reliable data from diverse sources. Expanding the analysis to include underexplored areas like vertical urban growth and refining data collection methods will offer a more complete understanding of urban development.

5. Conclusion

This study applied a volumetric framework to analyze the spatial and temporal evolution of urban growth in the Tehran Metropolitan Region (TMR) between 1985 and 2024. By examining three-dimensional urban form, including both horizontal expansion and vertical densification, and employing multi-phase analysis alongside machine learning-based interpretation of spatial drivers, the study provides a comprehensive understanding of how built form interacts with infrastructure, economic forces, and policy environments over time.

The findings reveal a complex and non-linear pattern of urban development. In the earlier phases, upward and outward expansion evolved in relative balance. However, in more recent years, horizontal sprawl has intensified, particularly through the emergence of large, low-density suburban developments. These peripheral areas have significantly extended the urban footprint of the TMR, while vertical intensification has continued in older central districts, although in an uneven and often disconnected manner. This divergence indicates a shift in urban morphology, from a compact and centralized form to one that is increasingly fragmented and spatially dispersed. The observed decline in population density per unit of built volume raises concerns about the

sustainability, efficiency, and livability of current development trajectories.

The study also highlights the importance of historical urban structure, infrastructure investment, and economic pressures in shaping growth patterns. High-density areas with established built environments have continued to attract vertical redevelopment due to their locational advantages and accumulated economic assets. At the same time, government-backed mass housing initiatives and speculative land-holding have driven outward expansion, frequently ahead of infrastructure provision or effective regulatory oversight. These dual processes have produced a region marked by spatial contradictions, where congested urban cores coexist with under-utilized, car-dependent suburban neighborhoods.

The development patterns observed in the TMR reflect trends found in many rapidly urbanizing cities in the Global South. In such contexts, rapid population growth, land market instability, and limited planning capacity often result in hybrid forms of urban expansion that combine dense inner-city growth with uncoordinated peripheral sprawl. Volumetric analysis offers a valuable perspective in this regard. It enables the identification of both horizontal and vertical growth processes and helps reveal their spatial relationships and associated challenges. Moreover, this approach exposes the limitations of two-dimensional measurements of urban extent, especially in cities undergoing vertical transformation where land scarcity and redevelopment pressures are intense.

A central insight of this study is the significance of achieving optimal density. This refers to a level of urban compactness that maximizes land and infrastructure efficiency while maintaining environmental integrity, livability, and social inclusion. In the TMR, deviations from this balance are evident. In some districts, density exceeds infrastructure capacity and undermines service quality. In others, excessively low densities in peripheral areas reduce public transport viability and increase environmental costs. Effective urban management requires careful calibration of density through context-sensitive planning and regulation that links built form with infrastructure readiness, ecological resilience, and accessibility.

To ensure more sustainable growth, the TMR must adopt integrated planning frameworks that coordinate land use, housing, infrastructure, and environmental policy. A polycentric spatial structure that fosters inclusive densification in established neighborhoods and promotes transit-oriented, medium-density development in suburban nodes is essential. Policies should also prioritize the upgrading of informal settlements, the regulation of speculative land practices, and the mitigation of environmental and seismic risks. The urban transformation of the TMR reflects the broader challenges faced by fast-growing cities worldwide. It underscores the need to reconsider how urban form is conceptualized, measured, and governed. Volumetric analysis, as demonstrated in this study, offers a practical and theoretical foundation for understanding spatial growth and guiding more resilient, efficient, and equitable urban futures.

Abbreviation	Full Name	Short Description
UVG	Urban Vertical Growth	Refers to the upward expansion of urban areas, typically through high-rise buildings.
GHSL	Global Human Settlement Layer	A dataset providing global spatial information about human settlements.
TMR	Tehran Metropolitan Region	The metropolitan area surrounding Tehran, Iran.
LISA	Local Indicators of Spatial Association	A statistical method to identify spatial clustering or patterns in data.
GWR	Geographically Weighted Regression	A local regression technique that models spatial variations in relationships.
GEE	Google Earth Engine	A cloud-based platform for planetary-scale environmental data analysis.

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Abbreviation	Full Name	Short Description
TM	Thematic Mapper	A sensor on the Landsat satellite used for Earth observation.
USGS	United States Geological Survey	A U.S. government agency responsible for Earth science research and data.
ETM+	Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus	An advanced sensor on Landsat 7 for Earth observation with improved capabilities.
OLI	Operational Land Imager	A sensor on Landsat 8 for capturing Earth's surface imagery.
MLC	Maximum Likelihood Classification	A statistical method for classifying data based on probability.
GIS	Geographic Information Systems	Systems for capturing, storing, and analyzing spatial and geographic data.
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar	A radar imaging technique used to create high-resolution images of the Earth.
DEMs	Digital Elevation Models	Digital representations of terrain elevation data.
ALOS PALSAR	Advanced Land Observing Satellite Phased Array Type L-band SAR sensor	A radar sensor on the ALOS satellite for Earth observation.
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging	A remote sensing method using laser pulses to measure distances and create 3D maps.
SS-coMCRF	Similarity-enhanced Markov chain random field cosimulation	A geostatistical method for spatial data simulation and modeling.
FAR	Floor Area Ratio	A measure of building density, calculated as the ratio of total floor area to land area.
SHAP	SHapley Additive exPlanations	A method for explaining the output of machine learning models.
XGBoost	eXtreme Gradient Boosting	A scalable and efficient machine learning algorithm for supervised learning.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ali Soltani: Writing – original draft, Project administration, Investigation, Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Alireza Dehghani:** Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Conceptualization, Validation, Resources, Formal analysis. **Parviz Azizi:** Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Data curation, Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Software, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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